

Detecting Literary Evaluations: Can Large Language Models Compete with Human Annotators?

Ilyas, Salmoon

salmoonilyas@gmail.com

Trier Center for Digital Humanities, Deutschland

ORCID: 0009-0007-6787-0069

Gittel, Benjamin

gittel@uni-trier.de

Trier Center for Digital Humanities, Deutschland

ORCID: 0000-0002-1855-0049

Introduction

One of the most complex and multi-layered phenomena when analyzing fictional narratives are literary evaluations, i.e. the ascriptions of a positive or negative property to fictional entities like characters, spaces, or events that occur in such texts (Hunt and Vipond 1986; Prinz and Winko 2013; Winko 1991). Correctly identifying literary evaluations is crucial for an adequate interpretation of the corresponding texts. Such evaluations can be verbal (e.g., "the bad guy") or non-verbal (e.g., spitting at someone's feet). They can be expressed through noun phrases, clauses, or concatenated clauses, and they can be explicit or highly implicit, demanding complex inferences for their identification. Especially the last feature makes them a challenge for humans, but also for automatic annotation. In this paper, we analyze how well current Large Language Models (henceforth LLMs) perform the identification of literary evaluations. Since LLMs have been successfully used in the recent past for the identification of various literary phenomena (Garret Raja Immanuel and Nevedha Liz Gloria 2024; Troiano and Vossen 2024; Hicke et al., 2025; Pagel, Pichler et al., 2024), they seem promising for the detection of an elusive phenomenon like literary evaluations that state of the art sentiment analysis tools struggle to detect (Gittel and Beider Wieden 2024).

The paper addresses the following research questions:

(RQI) How reliably can LLMs detect literary evaluations compared to human annotators?

(RQII) Do human annotators and LLMs struggle with the same literary texts, and to which textual features are these difficulties related?

(RQIII) Which type of literary evaluations are easier for LLMs to detect: noun-phrases or clause evaluations?

(RQIV) Are modern literary texts easier for LLMs to annotate than texts from the nineteenth century?

We use the annotation corpus "Evaluative Structures in Narrative Fiction" (Gittel 2025), which consists of 35 German-language fictional narratives. We evaluated the LLM annotations against the gold standard from this dataset treating the LLMs just like a human annotator.

Dataset and manual annotation

The annotation corpus "Evaluative Structures in Narrative Fiction" (Gittel 2025) consists of 35 German-language fictional narratives published between 1800 and 2015. All texts have been annotated by two annotators with a background in literary studies using the INCEpTION platform (Klie et al., 2018). A consensus-based gold standard has been created under the supervision of a literary expert. The mean agreement between annotators for evaluations (spans) for all 35 texts is 0.53 Mathet.2015's γ (2015). According to the annotation guidelines (Gittel forthcoming), minimal spans are noun phrases (NPs) or clauses. A NP-evaluation for example could be "Ein gewaltiger Mann" ("a mighty man") and a clause-evaluation could be "ihr Anblick hatte etwas Gerüstetes, Mutiges" ("there was something armoured and courageous about her appearance", Joseph Roth, our transl.). An implicit evaluation would be "den Philosophen mit dem Äußern eines Känguruhs" ("the philosopher with the appearance of a kangaroo", Thomas Mann, our transl.). Implicit evaluations can be understood "to be evaluative on the basis of pragmatic, cultural, or common knowledge shared by authors and readers" (Benamara et al., 2017, 215) while explicit evaluations contain "evaluative expressions at the textual surface" (Prinz and Winko 2013, 405 (my transl.)).

The evaluations were labeled by human annotators as positive or negative (polarity). Other annotation categories which are not relevant in the context of this paper included evaluator, evaluation target, and evaluated aspect. From the curated dataset of 35 documents, 10 were selected due to resource constraints. The sample was selected based on publication year (from the 19th and 20th century), varying text complexity and document length.

Pre-processing and Text segmentation

The document text and gold-standard evaluations including polarity labels, were extracted from curated data from INCEpTION (Klie et al., 2018) using dkpro-cassis (Klie and de Castilho n.d.) library. The document texts were cleaned, and special characters were removed. Since we are interested in the differences between NP and clause evaluations (cf. RQ III), the dependency parser ParZu (Sennrich 2013) was used for text segmentation. For all ten documents in our sample, we extracted clauses (finite verbs and their

dependent parts) and noun phrases (nouns and their dependent parts) (Hunter 2007).

Prompt-engineering

LLMs were tested using the same set of prompts with system and user roles (prompts are shared on GitHub; see references (Ilyas 2025)). The system role prompt identified the model as "expert in linguistics and literary studies". Only one system role prompt is used. Complete document text was provided to LLMs along with the prompt, to give the context of the clauses and noun phrases. We used three types of user prompts: Short prompt without examples (in the following "SHORT"), Short prompt with examples ("SHORT-EX"), and Long Prompt with examples and additional explanations ("LONG"). The user prompts contained the list of noun phrases and clauses to be classified as "positive", "negative" or "neutral" (no evaluation). The models returned the results in JSON format.

Evaluation

Three LLMs were used to identify literary evaluations: ChatGPT-4o (OpenAi), DeepSeek-R1-0528 (2025), and LLaMA 3.1 SauerkrautLM-70B-Instruct (VAGOsolutions). Paid versions of ChatGPT and DeepSeek were used, and the LLaMA Sauerkraut-LM was used by utilizing the computational resources generously provided by the Scientific Computing Cluster at GWDG (GWDC). To improve consistency, each model was run three times using major vote afterwards. Inter-annotator agreement between gold-standard and LLM's major vote, as well as between the human annotators, was calculated using Pygamma (Titeux and Riad 2021). Mathet.2015's Gamma (Mathet et al., 2015) is a measure that is especially useful if annotations contain overlapping segments or segments of different lengths, as in our case, because clauses usually contain NPs.

Results

The results are presented according to the four research questions formulated above.

RQ1: LLMs vs human annotators

The results indicate that LLMs are less reliable than human annotators in detecting literary evaluations across the sampled texts as human agreement score was substantially higher at 0.4296 compared to average LLMs score of 0.3176 (see Table 1). The highest-performing configurations across all models used the LONG prompt, with Deepseek achieving the highest average agreement score ($M = 0.3405$), followed closely by ChatGPT ($M = 0.3345$) and Llama Sauerkraut-LM ($M = 0.3302$).

Table 1. Agreement score for each LLM against the gold standard

LLM annotators	Prompt	Mean	SD	Var
Deepseek	LONG	0.3405	0.0968	0.0094
ChatGPT	LONG	0.3345	0.0647	0.0042
Llama Sauerkraut-LM	LONG	0.3302	0.0751	0.0056
Llama Sauerkraut-LM	SHORT_EX	0.3285	0.0677	0.0046
Llama Sauerkraut-LM	SHORT	0.3199	0.0906	0.0082
ChatGPT	SHORT_EX	0.3178	0.0825	0.0068
Deepseek	SHORT_EX	0.3058	0.0960	0.0092
ChatGPT	SHORT	0.2973	0.0642	0.0041
Deepseek	SHORT	0.2842	0.0837	0.0070
<i>Average</i>	-	0.3176	0.0801	0.0066

Note. SD = Standard deviation; Var = Variance; Mean Agreement Score (Humans) = 0.4296

Further insights can be drawn from agreement scores for each document for best model prompt combination (see Table 2). LLMs performance is found to be highly variable across texts. For instance, LLMs outperformed human annotators in "Mann: Der Geburtstag der Frau Baronin" (LLMs: 0.4371; Humans: 0.2436) and performed comparably in "Walser: Der Nachen" (LLMs: 0.3188; Humans: 0.3077). However, they fell notably short in others, such as "Grimm: Frau Holle" (LLMs: 0.3503; Humans: 0.6155) and "Grün: Liebe" (LLMs: 0.3098; Humans: 0.6527). This indicates that the models' reliability is text-dependent, with better performance on some documents and substantial deficits on others.

Table 2. Average Agreement Score for Each Document by LLMs (Best model prompt combination) and Humans

Document Title	Mean Ag. (Deepseek)	Mean Ag. (ChatGPT)	Mean Ag. (Llama)	Mean Ag. (LLMs)	Mean Ag. (Humans)
Mann: Der Geburtstag der Frau Baronin	0.4411	0.4441	0.4324	0.4371	0.2436
Storm: Im Saal	0.4170	0.3631	0.3962	0.3991	0.4904
Grimm: Frau Holle	0.3482	0.3033	0.3868	0.3503	0.6155
Löns: Die beiden Höfe	0.4834	0.3393	0.3648	0.3408	0.2768
Walser: Der Nachen	0.2476	0.4446	0.3825	0.3188	0.3077
Grün: Liebe	0.3483	0.2876	0.3101	0.3098	0.6527
Heym: Die Sektion	0.3942	0.3142	0.3170	0.2968	0.4438
Heckmann: Das Henkersmahl	0.2852	0.3090	0.2459	0.2652	0.4320
Altenberg: Die Natur	0.1747	0.2786	0.2669	0.2415	0.4972
Hebel: Unverhofftes Wiedersehen	0.2654	0.2611	0.1994	0.2169	0.3365
<i>Average</i>	0.3405	0.3345	0.3302	0.31763	0.4296

Note. Llama = Llama Sauerkraut-LM; Ag. Agreement Score; LLMs = Large Language Models.

While all LLMs show some ability to detect literary evaluations, their lower overall mean agreement highlights inconsistencies. This implies that while LLMs can spot literary evaluations to a limited extent, their proficiency remains relative to other literary aspects which could be investigated in future research.

RQ2: Difficulties with specific literary texts

Our investigation reveals that human annotators and LLMs do not struggle with the same literary texts (see Table 3). Document-level analysis reveals a wide range of LLM and human agreement scores where higher values indicate that a document was easier to annotate for both. For example, "Mann: Der Geburtstag der Frau Baronin" shows the highest LLM agreement score (0.4371), but the lowest human agreement score of 0.2436. Whereas "Heckmann: Das Henkersmahl" has a low LLM agreement score (0.2652) but has a relatively high human agreement score (0.4320).

Table 3. Average Agreement Score for Each Document by LLMs and Humans

Agreement Category (LLMs)	Document Title	Token Count	Sentence Count	Mean Agreement (LLMs)	Mean Agreement (Humans)
High	Mann: Der Geburtstag der Frau Baronin	2243	48	0.4371	0.2436
	Storm: Im Saal	2466	79	0.3991	0.4904
	Grimm: Frau Holle	952	33	0.3503	0.6155
Mid	Löns: Die beiden Höfe	1428	39	0.3408	0.2768
	Walser: Der Nachen	310	20	0.3188	0.3077
	Grün: Liebe	326	22	0.3098	0.6527
	Heym: Die Sektion	750	38	0.2968	0.4438
Low	Heckmann: Das Henkersmahl	617	25	0.2652	0.4320
	Altenberg: Die Natur	534	24	0.2415	0.4972
	Hebel: Unverhofftes Wiedersehen	856	18	0.2169	0.3365
Mean	-	1048	34	0.3176	0.4296

These findings suggest that LLMs and humans face quite different challenges with certain texts. There seem to be underlying factors (textual properties) which have different effects on the LLMs agreement scores and human agreement scores.

RQ3: Noun Phrases vs. Clauses

Total number of clauses and noun phrases in all ten documents given to LLMs for evaluations detection were 857 and 1,536, respectively. We find that for all LLMs evaluations in the clauses are easier to detect for LLMs than the noun phrases, as clause evaluation detection rates are consistently higher than NP-evaluation detection rates (see Table 4). Interestingly, one can observe that clause and NP detection rates are not dependent on the prompt, but only on the model as on average Llama Sauerkraut-LM consistently performed worst among all three LLMs and for all three prompts. Deepseek and ChatGPT were the best in identifying the clauses and NP evaluations with the average detection rate of the clauses above 31% and NP evaluations above 21% for both.

Table 4. Average Performance of LLMs on Identification of Evaluations in all documents

Model Name	Prompt	Clause Detection Rate	NP Detection Rate
Deepseek	SHORT	39.91%	22.40%
ChatGPT	SHORT	38.62%	25.52%
Deepseek	SHORT_EX	38.51%	21.29%
ChatGPT	SHORT_EX	32.56%	21.74%
Deepseek	LONG	32.44%	17.90%
ChatGPT	LONG	31.74%	21.81%
Llama Sauerkraut-LM	SHORT	31.16%	16.80%
Llama Sauerkraut-LM	LONG	28.47%	16.21%
Llama Sauerkraut-LM	SHORT_EX	27.30%	17.84%
Average.	-	33.41%	20.17%

We believe that higher clauses detection rates relative to NP evaluation detection rates is a rather surprising finding which calls for further investigation, because noun phrase evaluations are often semantic in nature (e.g. "the evil guy") and the easiest to identify with more traditional NLP-methods (e.g. dictionary-based).

RQ4: Modern vs. 19th century texts

Our findings demonstrate that there is no clear relationship of the publication year of literary texts (as proxy for linguistic modernity) with neither LLM annotation nor human annotation scores (see Table 5). Although some 19th-century texts such as "Mann: Der Geburtstag der Frau Baronin" (1889, mean = 0.4371) and "Storm: Im Saal" (1851, mean = 0.3991) achieved the highest mean agreement scores with LLM annotators indicating strong LLM performance, but others from the same century, such as "Hebel: Unverhofftes Wiedersehen" (1811, mean = 0.2169) and "Altenberg: Die Natur" (1896, mean = 0.2415), showed the lowest scores. In contrast, many 20th century texts lie in the mid (between 0.30 to 0.35) performance range.

Table 5. Average Agreement Score for Each Document by LLMs and Humans

Century	Document Title	Token Count	Sentence Count	Year	Mean Ag. (LLMs)	Mean Ag. (Humans)
19th	Hebel: Unverhofftes Wiedersehen	856	18	1811	0.2169	0.3365
	Grimm: Frau Holle	952	33	1812	0.3503	0.6155
	Storm: Im Saal	2466	79	1851	0.3991	0.4904
	Mann: Der Geburtstag der Frau Baronin	2243	48	1889	0.4371	0.2436
	Altenberg: Die Natur	534	24	1896	0.2415	0.4972
Mean(19th)	-	1410	40	-	0.3290	0.4366
20th	Heym: Die Sektion	750	38	1913	0.2968	0.4438
	Walser: Der Nachen	310	20	1914	0.3188	0.3077
	Löns: Die beiden Höfe	1428	39	1916	0.3408	0.2768
	Grün: Liebe	326	22	1932	0.3098	0.6527
	Heckmann: Das Henkersmahl	617	25	1964	0.2652	0.4320
Mean(20th)	-	686	28	-	0.3063	0.4226
Mean(both)	-	1048	34	-	0.3176	0.4296

Note. Ag. Agreement Score; LLMs = Large Language Models.

Something very similar can be observed for the human annotators: A document from the 20th century such as "Grün: Liebe" had the highest agreement score of 0.6527 and "Löns: Die beiden Höfe" (1916, mean = 0.2768) from the same period had the lowest score. For the 19th century, "Grimm: Frau Holle" (1812, mean=0.6155) got the highest mean score by human annotators, while another, namely "Mann: Der Geburtstag der Frau Baronin" (1889, mean = 0.2436), ranked the lowest among the 10 documents. In case of human annotators some documents belonging to both 19th and 20th century also lay in the mid (between 0.30 - 0.45) performance range. These mixed results for both LLMs and human annotators suggest that LLM annotation performance is not determined by publication year alone. Instead, it likely depends on a combination of textual features, such as sentence complexity, narrative structure, and lexical choices, rather than on a linear relationship with linguistic modernity, which requires further investigation.

Bibliography

Deepseek. n.d. "DeepSeek API." <https://github.com/deepseek-ai>.

DeepSeek-AI. 2025. "DeepSeek-R1: Incentivizing Reasoning Capability in LLMs via Reinforcement Learning." *DeepSeek-R1: Incentivizing Reasoning Capability in LLMs via Reinforcement Learning*. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2501.12948>.

- Garret Raja Immanuel, S., and P. Nevedha Liz Gloria.** 2024. "AI-Driven Literary Analysis: Exploring the Role of ChatGPT in Understanding and Interpreting Literary Texts." *Bodhi International Journal of Research in Humanities, Arts and Science* 8. https://www.bodhijournals.com/pdf/V8N2/Bodhi_V8N2_009.pdf.
- Gittel, Benjamin.** forthcoming. "Annotationsrichtlinien für Evaluative Textstrukturen: Literarische Wertungen, Codierungen, und Oppositionen."
- Gittel, Benjamin.** 2025. "Evaluative Structures in Narrative Fiction." (Zenodo). doi:10.5281/zenodo.16570556.
- Gittel, Benjamin, and Gesa Bei der Wieden.** 2024. "Exploring Fictional Critique and Literary Evaluations ." *Exploring Fictional Critique and Literary Evaluations* . Zenodo, October. doi:10.5281/zenodo.13934975.
- GWDC.** n.d. *GWDC - Scientific Compute Cluster*. <https://docs.hpc.gwdg.de/acknowledgements/index.html#scientific-compute-cluster>.
- Harris, Charles R., K. Jarrod Millman, Stéfan J. Van Der Walt, Ralf Gommers, Pauli Virtanen, David Cournapeau, Eric Wieser, et al.** 2020. "Array programming with NumPy." *Nature* 585: 357–362. Accessed August 1, 2025. doi:10.1038/s41586-020-2649-2.
- Havrylash, Julia, Evgeniia Fileva, Ruth Bruchertseifer, and Christof Schöch.** 2025. "CLS INFRA D3.4 Position papers and pilot studies on emerging trends in CLS ." *CLS INFRA D3.4 Position papers and pilot studies on emerging trends in CLS* . Zenodo, March. doi:10.5281/zenodo.15131773.
- Hicke, Rebecca M. M., Yuri Bizzoni, Pascale Feldkamp, and Ross Deans Kristensen-McLachlan.** 2025. "Says Who? Effective Zero-Shot Annotation of Focalization." *Says Who? Effective Zero-Shot Annotation of Focalization*. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2409.11390>.
- Hunt, Russel A., and Douglas Vipond.** 1986. "Evaluations in literary reading." *Text - Interdisciplinary Journal for the Study of Discourse* 6: 53–72. doi:doi:10.1515/text.1.1986.6.1.53.
- Hunter, J. D.** 2007. "Matplotlib: A 2D graphics environment." *Computing in Science & Engineering* (IEEE COMPUTER SOC) 9: 90–95. doi:10.1109/MCSE.2007.55.
- Ilyas, Salmoon.** 2025. "Detecting Literary Evaluations (Github repo)." *Detecting Literary Evaluations (Github repo)*. <https://github.com/salmoonilyas/detecting-literary-evaluations>.
- Klie, Jan-Christoph, and Richard Eckart de Castilho.** n.d. "DKPro Cassis - Reading and Writing UIMA CAS Files in Python." *DKPro Cassis - Reading and Writing UIMA CAS Files in Python*. Zenodo. doi:10.5281/zenodo.3994108.
- Klie, Jan-Christoph, Michael Bugert, Beto Boulosa, Richard Eckart de Castilho, and Iryna Gurevych.** 2018. "The INCEption Platform: Machine-Assisted and Knowledge-Oriented Interactive Annotation." *Proceedings of the 27th International Conference on Computational Linguistics: System Demonstrations*. Santa, Fe: Association for Computational Linguistics. 5–9. <http://tubiblio.ulb.tu-darmstadt.de/106270/>.
- Mathet, Yann, Antoine Widlöcher, and Jean-Philippe Métivier.** 2015. "The Unified and Holistic Method Gamma (γ) for Inter-Annotator Agreement Measure and Alignment." *Computational Linguistics* 41: 437–479. doi:10.1162/COLI_a_00227.
- McKinney, Wes.** 2010. "Data Structures for Statistical Computing in Python." Austin, Texas. 56–61. Accessed August 1, 2025. doi:10.25080/Majora-92bf1922-00a.
- OpenAi.** n.d. "openai/openai-python." *openai/openai-python*. OpenAI. Accessed August 1, 2025. <https://github.com/openai/openai-python>.
- Pagel, Janis, Axel Pichler, and Nils Reiter.** 2024. "Evaluating In-Context Learning for Computational Literary Studies: A Case Study Based on the Automatic Recognition of Knowledge Transfer in German Drama." Edited by Yuri Bizzoni, Stefania Degaetano-Ortlieb, Anna Kazantseva and Stan Szpakowicz. *Proceedings of the 8th Joint SIGHUM Workshop on Computational Linguistics for Cultural Heritage, Social Sciences, Humanities and Literature (LaTeCH-CLfL 2024)*. St. Julians, Malta: Association for Computational Linguistics. 1–10. <https://aclanthology.org/2024.latechclfl-1.1/>.
- Prinz, Katharina, and Simone Winko.** 2013. "Handbuch Kanon und Wertung: Theorien, Instanzen, Geschichte." Chap. Wie rekonstruiert man Wertungen und Werte in literarischen Texten., 402–407. J.B. Metzler.
- Prinz, Katharina, and Simone Winko.** 2013. "Wie rekonstruiert man Wertungen und Werte in literarischen Texten?" In *Handbuch Kanon und Wertung. Theorien, Instanzen, Geschichte*, edited by Gabriele Rippl and Simone Winko, 402–407. Stuttgart/Weimar: J. B. Metzler.
- Sennrich, Rico.** 2013. "A New Hybrid Dependency Parser for German." *Proceedings of the GSCL 2013*. <https://github.com/rsennrich/ParZu>.
- Smith, S. A., T. O. Levante, B. H. Meier, J. Magn. Reson., and R. R. Ernst.** 1994. "Computer Simulations in Magnetic Resonance. An Object-Oriented Programming Approach." *Journal of Magnetic Resonance, Series A* 106: 75–105. doi:https://doi.org/10.1006/jmra.1994.1008.
- Titeux, Hadrien, and Rachid Riad.** 2021. "pygamma-agreement: Gamma γ measure for inter/intra-annotator agreement in Python." *Journal of Open Source Software* 6: 2989. doi:10.21105/joss.02989 .
- Troiano, Enrica, and Piek T. J. M. Vossen.** 2024. "CLAUSE-ATLAS: A Corpus of Narrative Information to Scale up Computational Literary Analysis." Edited by Nicoletta Calzolari, Min-Yen Kan, Veronique Hoste, Alessandro Lenci, Sakriani Sakti and Nianwen Xue. *Proceedings of the 2024 Joint International Conference on Computational Linguistics, Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC-COLING 2024)*. Torino, Italia: ELRA and ICCL. 3283–3296. <https://aclanthology.org/2024.lrec-main.292/>.
- VAGOsolutions.** n.d. "VAGOsolutions/Llama-3-SauerkrautLM-70b-Instruct · Hugging Face."

VAGOsolutions/Llama-3-SauerkrautLM-70b-Instruct ·
Hugging Face. Accessed August 1,
2025. <https://huggingface.co/VAGOsolutions/Llama-3-SauerkrautLM-70b-Instruct>.

Winko, Simone. 1991. *Wertungen und Werte in Texten*.
Springer.